

Factors Shaping Functional Food Purchase and Consumption Intention: Insights from the Eastern Mediterranean Region of Türkiye

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine consumers' awareness and consumption frequency towards selected functional food products and to investigate the relationship between consumers' attitudes, socio-demographic characteristics and their purchase and consumption intention towards functional foods in Türkiye. We conducted an online survey with 384 respondents, almost equally distributed between genders, from the Eastern Mediterranean Region of Türkiye. According to the result of the factor analysis, we found 5 factors named "Reward", "Confidence", "Purchase and Consumption Intention", "Safety" and "Necessity". The t-test and One Way ANOVA analyses conducted links between consumers' socio-demographics and their intentions to purchase and consumption intention to functional foods. Results confirm that mainly female respondents and those with higher education have more positive intentions to buy and consume functional foods. Additionally, multiple linear regression analysis results revealed significant positive associations between consumers' attitudes regarding confidence and reward from using functional foods (FFs) and their purchase and consumption intention (PCI). Conversely, significant and negative associations were found between consumers' attitudes regarding the necessity for FFs and their PCI. Also, the most consumed functional foods were Turkish coffee, pickles and mineral water by consumers. Our paper offers strategic insights for businesses and marketers seeking to tailor approaches and enhance appeal to diverse consumer segments in the competitive landscape of functional foods.

Keywords: *functional foods, consumer behavior, purchase and consumption intention, Eastern Mediterranean Region of Türkiye.*

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Introduction

Today, with the increasing health awareness and the desire to live a long life, consumers are turning to healthier and more qualified foods. Consumers' current patterns in food consumption indicate a growing awareness of the correlation between diet and health, with a recognition that incorporating innovative products with health claims into their diet can contribute to a lowered risk of diseases (Annunziata and Vecchio, 2013; Vecchio et al., 2016). Around two millennia ago, Hippocrates stressed the significance of

food in relation to human health, famously stating, "Let food be thy medicine and medicine be thy food" (Bagchi, 2014). The concept of "diet" predates the emergence of nutritional science in the 1800s; however, significant strides have been made by scientists since the 1970s to provide recommendations for daily nutrient intake to promote and sustain human well-being (Martirosyan and Singh, 2015). In the 21st century, nutritional science has achieved significant milestones, including the identification of nutrients, formulation of dietary guidelines, and development of dynamic food products, all aimed at addressing malnutrition and promoting healthier dietary practices by minimizing the consumption of harmful substances (Welsch, 1996).

The notion of functional food was initially introduced in the 1980s within Japan (Arai, 2002). Notably, Japan stands as the pioneer and sole country to implement a dedicated regulatory approval process for functional foods (Arai, 2002; Kojima, 1996). In 1991, the Ministry of Health, Labor, and Welfare (MHLW) of Japan published a regulation known as "Foods for Specific Health Uses" (FOSHU). This regulatory framework facilitated the development and introduction of new products, with many items that demonstrated health benefits through clinical trials making their way into the market (Iwatani and Yamamoto, 2019). Since the 1990s, Finland has actively developed and discussed the concept of functional foods, while the acceptance of these foods in the Western world gained traction in the late 1990s (Puhakka et al., 2017; Di Pasquale et al., 2011). Functional foods have been defined in various ways. For instance, in the study conducted by Urala and Lähteenmäki (2004), functional foods were described as "a new type of food that promises improvement in the physiological functions of the body". On the other hand, in a study by Boluda and Capilla (2017), functional foods were defined as "functional foods are foods that contain various components to improve health status or reduce the risk of disease". Functional foods are classified in more than one category. Accordingly, a functional food is (1) a natural food, (2) a beneficial ingredient has been added, (3) a harmful ingredient has been removed, (4) one or more ingredients have been modified, (5) its bioavailability has been altered, or (6) can be any combination of these (Henry, 2010).

The increasing popularity of functional foods can be attributed to a growing awareness of personal health among consumers. Based on a survey conducted by Euromonitor, Japan holds the position of the world's largest functional foods market, followed by the United States, while the European market is still relatively less developed in comparison. These three major markets collectively account for more than 90% of the total sales (Benkouider, 2005). Among the European countries, Germany, France, and Italy are particularly noteworthy as significant functional food markets, whereas Hungary, Poland, and Russia are categorized as emerging markets in this sector (Bigliardi and Galati, 2013). The global probiotic market is anticipated to grow at a rate of 7.3%, reaching an estimated value of \$74.7 billion by 2025 from \$42.5 billion in 2017, with functional foods and beverages holding a substantial market share of 76.4% in 2017 (IFT, 2020). Notably, one-third of Chinese parents express an interest in high-fiber foods for their children, while 54% of Indian consumers seek to incorporate more fiber into their diets (IFT, 2020). In 2017, Asia became the world's largest dietary supplement market, with global sales reaching \$128.3 billion, driven by remarkable growth rates in China, Eastern Europe/Russia, Latin America, and Africa, exceeding 9% year-over-year (IFT, 2020). The functional food market size in Türkiye was around 5.8 million dollars in 2017, and the market volume increased by 10% compared to the previous year (Gök and Ulu, 2018). While the highest increase among functional foods occurred in dairy products with an increase of 25%, the functional food market size of Türkiye is expected to reach 360 million dollars in 2021 (Gök and Ulu, 2018).

In Türkiye, particularly among urban middle, upper-middle, and upper-class consumers, the increasing level of knowledge in health-related matters has led to a growing number of "functional/enriched" packaged products in the market (USDA, 2019). In recent years, the media in Türkiye has focused on the harmful effects of sugar and saturated fat, which are among the increasing issues related to obesity

and diabetes (USDA, 2019). Additionally, well-educated parents with higher disposable incomes place great importance on the nutritional content of the food they provide to their children (USDA, 2019).

In the realm of Turkish literature, previous studies have delved into consumers' attitudes and behaviors towards functional foods (Seçer et al., 2014; Gezginç and Gök, 2016; Eser, 2017; Sevilmiş et al., 2017; Altindiş et al., 2018; Yilmaz-Ersan et al., 2020, Çelik et al., 2021; Çelik, 2023; Kurkcu et al., 2023). This study distinguishes from others in several aspects. Unlike previous research conducted on a local scale, our study adopts a regional perspective, encompassing the broader context of the Eastern Mediterranean Region of Türkiye. Our research breaks conventional boundaries by encompassing traditional functional foods in Türkiye, notably highlighting health-supporting products such as fermented black carrot juice (Şalgam), tarhana chips and soup (Gök, 2023). Our study aimed to address a gap in Turkish literature by examining the awareness and consumption frequency of selected functional foods among consumers. Additionally, we aimed to investigate consumers' purchase and consumption intentions towards functional foods, examining how these intentions may be influenced by their attitudes and socio-demographic characteristics. To contribute to the existing body of knowledge, our research encompasses almost all of the Eastern Mediterranean Region of Türkiye, providing an original perspective by comparing and analyzing the holistic consumer trends and intentions towards functional foods across this diverse area.

Literature Review

Several researches have already examined on consumer attitudes and behaviors towards functional foods. The study conducted by Verbeke (2005) indicated that beliefs, knowledge, and control over health played significant roles in influencing the acceptance of functional foods. The findings further supported the notion of a rational and cognitive decision-making process when it comes to functional food choices. In a separate study by Qin and Brown (2008), they explored variations in attitudes towards genetically modified foods based on consumers' gender. Their analysis revealed that trust in organizations, perceived risk, and heightened ethical concerns regarding these practices were the most influential factors in shaping attitudes towards purchase intentions. In another study conducted by Jeżewska-Zychowicz (2009), the attitudes and purchasing tendencies of students toward functional foods were investigated. In the study, it was concluded that although the respondents were mostly familiar with functional foods, they did not consume them very often. However, the most consumed functional food by students was determined as probiotic yogurt. The study conducted by Boluda and Capilla (2017) in Spain investigated the influence of consumer attitudes on the selection and consumption of functional foods. The study surveyed 333 individuals, and the findings revealed that consumer attitudes towards functional foods directly impact their willingness to consume such products. Interestingly, the study also found that having a healthy lifestyle did not affect these attitudes, but lifestyle factors had a negative influence on the willingness to use functional foods. In another study conducted by Landström (2008), Swedish consumers' attitudes towards functional foods were investigated. According to the results, consumers wondered whether functional foods are normal foods or drugs. Although, consumers in the focus groups are primarily skeptical of functional foods, they found that these products are mostly consumed by people who are health-conscious, well-educated, and aware of the impact of foods. One other study conducted by Chen (2011) in Taiwan, explored the relationship between consumers' attitudes toward functional foods and their willingness to use these products. The findings revealed significant differences in attitudes and willingness to consume functional foods between the "Healthy Life Attentive" and "Healthy Life Inattentive" groups, highlighting the impact of individual characteristics and healthy lifestyles on consumer behavior in this context.

Socio-demographic characteristics have been identified as influential factors in consumers' acceptance of functional foods, as highlighted by several studies including Anttolainen et al., 2001, Verbeke (2005),

Teratanavat and Hooker, 2006, Ares and Gámbaro (2007), Niva and Mäkelä (2007), Markosyan et al. (2009), Markovina et al. (2011), Baglione et al. (2012), Ozen et al. (2013), Cavaliere et al. (2015), Kljusuric et al. (2015), Schnettler et al. (2015), Bekoglu et al. (2016), Kraus et al. (2017). Carrillo et al. (2013) specifically attributed the interest of young individuals in consuming functional foods to their open-mindedness and willingness to try novel food products. Additionally, various studies have emphasized that young adults constitute an important consumer group for future market growth and adoption of functional foods. In a study conducted by Labrecque et al (2006), the approaches of young consumers towards functional foods were investigated. In the study, data collected from business department students in Canada, the United States, and France were collected and they found that students did not have much knowledge about functional foods, but were willing to buy and associated functional foods with health. The study conducted by Urala and Lähteenmäki (2007) in Finland revealed that consumer attitudes towards functional foods are not only influenced by demographic factors but also by individual lifestyle choices. The findings indicated that consumers' lifestyles play a significant role in shaping their attitudes towards functional foods, which subsequently affect their willingness to use these products. In another study conducted by Urala et al. (2011) focusing on consumer perceptions of functional foods in the United States, the findings revealed that a significant portion of US consumers perceive functional foods as confusing and unreliable. Migliore et al. (2022) investigated the willingness to pay (WTP) among 110 Italian consumers for organic eggs enriched with omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), compared to standard organic eggs. The study found that over 73% of respondents were willing to pay an average premium of €0.16 for functional organic eggs. This preference was primarily influenced by both self-interest and a strong environmental attitude. Contini et al. (2023) used a structural equation model (SEM) to explore factors shaping attitudes toward functional foods. Positive attitudes were linked to psychographic traits, including interest in healthy eating, trust in the food chain, openness to new foods, and lower self-control. Sociodemographically, the most positive attitudes were found in young individuals with children under 12 and a middle or high school diploma. Fantechi et al. (2023) found that there is a substantial consumer segment interested in spirulina-based pasta and willing to pay an average premium of €1.28 for a 1-kg package. This segment comprises prevalently young, physically active, well-educated men, who are interested in healthy eating and open to trying new foods. They primarily have a plant-based diet and good familiarity with functional foods. Nazzaro et al. (2024) examine consumer acceptance of Omega-3 enriched olive oil and lutein-enriched pasta through a choice experiment with 445 Italian consumers. Price was the main factor influencing decisions, followed by the functional attribute. Consumers were willing to pay a premium for these functional foods, providing insights for practitioners and future research.

This topic also has been extensively explored in previous studies within the Turkish literature. For instance, according to Sevilmiş's (2008) research, younger and more educated Turkish consumers display a greater preference for consuming functional foods. In addition, The functional food purchase intentions of Turkish consumers are influenced by their knowledge of functional foods as well as their expectations regarding the level of benefit and taste they anticipate obtaining from consuming such products (Sevilmiş et al., 2017; Çelik et al., 2021; Çelik, 2023). In a study conducted by Eser (2017) in the Çanakkale province of Türkiye, an examination of consumer attitudes towards probiotic products revealed that around 71% of respondents incorporate probiotic products into their consumption habits. The findings indicated yogurt as the most commonly consumed probiotic product, with 10% of consumers reporting regular daily intake of such products. In a study conducted by Altındış et al. (2018) among family doctors in Türkiye, findings indicated that approximately 67% of respondents possessed a moderate level of knowledge regarding probiotics. The study also brought to light various concerns among the respondents regarding the safety of probiotics, underscoring the need for increased awareness and conscious information dissemination about the proper use of probiotics. In another study, Çelik and Gül (2023) highlight that health and food safety play a crucial role in consumer decisions regarding organic food, as evidenced by their study conducted in the eastern Mediterranean region of Türkiye.

Kurkcu et al. (2023) found that health anxiety and perceived social value positively influenced functional food consumption intentions among restaurant consumers in İstanbul, while health knowledge levels negatively moderated the relationship between health anxiety and these intentions.

Methodology

Research Model and Hypotheses

The preceding literature reviews on attitudes and behaviors toward functional foods delved into four distinct areas influencing consumers' intentions to purchase and consume such products (Urala and Lähteenmäki, 2004; 2007). This chapter also explores the relationship between socio-demographics and the intention to purchase and consume functional foods, providing the framework for the proposed research model (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

Based on the research model, the hypotheses for the study are outlined below:

H1. There are statistically significant relationships between consumers' attitudes towards functional foods and their purchase and consumption intention.

H1a. There is a statistically significant relationship between consumers' attitudes regarding Safety of functional foods and their purchase and consumption intention.

H1b. There is a statistically significant relationship between consumers' attitudes regarding Reward from using functional foods and their purchase and consumption intention.

H1c. There is a statistically significant relationship between consumers' attitudes regarding Necessity for functional foods and their purchase and consumption intention.

H1d. There is a statistically significant relationship between consumers' attitudes regarding Confidence in functional foods and their purchase and consumption intention.

H2. There are statistically significant relationships between consumers' socio-demographic characteristics and their purchase and consumption intention.

H2a. There are statistically significant relationships between consumers' gender and their purchase and consumption intention.

H2b. There are statistically significant relationships between consumers' education degree and their purchase and consumption intention.

H2c. There are statistically significant relationships between consumers' occupation and their purchase and consumption intention.

H2d. There are statistically significant relationships between consumers' household size and their purchase and consumption intention.

Area of Study

Türkiye boasts a rich culinary culture shaped by centuries of diverse civilizations and historical influences. This study focuses on the Eastern Mediterranean region, renowned for its unique gastronomic traditions, agricultural and industrial potential, high urbanization, and dense population. Key cities in this region—Adana, Kahramanmaraş, Hatay, and Osmaniye—serve as vital industrial and cultural hubs, contributing to a dynamic consumer landscape. Adana, the sixth most populous city (2,258,718 in 2020), is celebrated for its agriculture and gastronomic heritage. Kahramanmaraş, the 11th largest province (1,168,163 in 2020), is famous for its unique ice cream. Osmaniye, with a population of 548,556, is bordered by Hatay, Adana, and Kahramanmaraş. Hatay, located on the southeastern Mediterranean coast, has a population of 1,628,894 and is characterized by its agricultural land (54.7%) and the Amanos Mountains. The study area reflects a diverse demographic profile, encompassing variations in gender, marital status, education, occupation, age, income, household size, and residence city. Figure 2 provides a map of Türkiye, highlighting the study region (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Climate Change, 2020a; 2020b; 2020c; Republic of Türkiye Hatay Governorship, 2023).

Figure 2. Study Area Map Covering the Eastern Mediterranean Region of Türkiye

Source: nationsonline.org

Data Collection

The research data was collected through an online survey conducted using Google Forms from February to June 2021. A random sample of 384 respondents was selected from the provinces of Adana (Çukurova

and Seyhan), Osmaniye (Center), Kahramanmaraş (Dulkadiroğlu and Onikisubat), and Hatay (Antakya), which are located in the East Mediterranean Region of Türkiye.

The socio-demographic characteristics of the consumers participating in the research are given in Table 1. According to the table, 52.1% of the respondents were female, 47.9% were male, while 62.2% were married and 37.8% were single, and 63.3% were between the ages of 18-35, and 29.1% were between the ages of 36-53. In addition, it was determined that 21% of the respondents were high school graduates and 50.8% were university graduates. In addition, 21.9% of respondents had master's or doctoral degrees. Also, 23.7% and 29.7% of respondents have an income between 2.826-4.000 TL and 4.001-6.000 TL.

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Residence City	N	%
Adana	184	48.0
Kahramanmaraş	95	24.7
Hatay	55	14.3
Osmaniye	50	13.0
Total	384	100.00
Gender		
Female	200	52.1
Male	184	47.9
Total	384	100.00
Marital Status		
Married	239	62.2
Single	145	37.8
Total	384	100.00
Education		
Primary Education	24	6.3
High School	81	21.0
University	195	50.8
Master or Doctoral Degree	84	21.9
Total	384	100.0
Occupation		
Private Sector	125	32.6
Government Employee	174	45.3
Retired	24	6.3
Student	21	5.5
Unemployed	40	10.3
Total	384	100.00
Age Group		
18-35	243	63.3
36-53	112	29.1
54-71	29	7.6
Total	384	100.00
Income		
Under 2.825 TL	59	15.4
Between 2.826-4.000 TL	91	23.7
Between 4.001-6.000 TL	114	29.7
6.000+	120	31.2
Total	384	100.00
Household Size		
1	41	10.7
2	56	14.6
3	106	27.6
4	100	26.0
5+	81	21.1
Total	384	100.0

Sample Size Determination Method

In order to reach the maximum sample in the research area, the P and Q values were taken into account as 0.50. Accordingly, the number of samples for the research was determined as 384 at 95% significance level and 5% margin of error (Churchill, 1995).

As a formula;

$$n = \left(\frac{Z_{\alpha/2}}{d} \right)^2 P \cdot Q$$

P: Positive probability (50%)

Q: 1-P Negative probability (50%)

$Z_{\alpha/2}$: Confidence interval (95%, table value 1.96)

d: Margin of error (5%)

$$n = \left(\frac{1.96}{0.05} \right)^2 0.50 * 0.50 = 384 \quad (1)$$

Survey Development and the Scale

The survey begins with socio-demographic questions, followed by an introduction to functional foods to ensure respondent understanding. Next, consumers were asked about their recognition and consumption frequency of specific functional foods (Table 3). Attitudes were measured using a 5-point Likert Scale based on Urala and Lahteenmaki (2004, 2007), covering Reward, Necessity, Confidence, Safety, and Purchase & Consumption Intention. Rewards relate to health and well-being, while necessity depends on perceived medical benefits. Confidence reflects trust in safety and effectiveness, and safety concerns potential risks. Purchase and consumption intention was assessed with three statements: PCI1. If functional foods are available, I buy it, PCI2. It is likely that I will purchase a functional food product soon, and PCI3. I willingly try even unfamiliar products if they are functional. The first two were adapted from Yeon Kim and Chung (2011), and the last from Urala and Lahteenmaki (2004).

Statistical Analyses

Factor analysis was employed as the primary method to streamline the multitude of variables, resulting in the creation of new factorial dimensions that combine the original predictors while minimizing the loss of variance. This analytical approach enabled the synthesis of information, highlighting the latent relationships among the initial variables (Gewers et. al., 2021). Factor analysis allowed us to condense information by emphasizing the underlying connections among the original variables (Nakip, 2006). We employed statistical tests, including t-tests and ANOVA, to explore the relationships between gender, marital status, and the intention to purchase and consume. These analyses also extend to other socio-demographic factors like income and education. The t-test, a commonly used statistical method, helps assess if there is a significant difference in means between two groups. The null hypothesis assumes that the means are equal, while the alternative hypothesis proposes a statistically significant difference between the means (Whitley, 2002; Sundaram et al., 2014). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is a statistical method for observing the relationship comparison of more than two groups (St and Wold, 1989). Additionally, multiple linear regression was employed in the model to elucidate the relationships between a single

dependent variable and multiple independent variables. With the aim of understanding how multiple independent variables collectively influence the dependent variable, this statistical analysis allows for a comprehensive examination of their interconnections (Nakip, 2006). The mathematical representation of the multiple linear regression model is presented below:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

Where Y represents the dependent variable, $X_1 + X_2 + X_3 + X_4$ denote the independent variables, β_0 is the intercept, $\beta_1 + \beta_2 + \beta_3 + \beta_4$ are the respective regression coefficients, and ϵ represents the error term (Equation 2).

Results

Table 2 (Appendix 1) presents the recognition and consumption frequency of various functional foods among the study respondents, as ranked on a 5-point Likert scale. The results indicate that the main functional food products regularly consumed by the respondents include Turkish coffee, pickles, mineral water, fish, tarhana and soup, radish, and fermented black carrot juice.

The rating scales of negatively worded items were reversed, and items with clearly skewed distributions were excluded from the analysis. Following this procedure, a final set of 20 statements was used for data analysis. To group the statements into independent subsets, factor analysis was performed using the Principal Component Analysis method with Varimax Rotation (Beardsworth et al., 1999). Before conducting the factor analysis, the suitability of the data was assessed using the Kaiser-Mayer-Olin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity. The KMO measure indicated a value of 0.890, surpassing the suggested cutoff of 0.60, indicating the sample size was appropriate for factor analysis (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2001). Furthermore, Bartlett's test of sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2=3205.517$, $df=91$, $p=0.000$), indicating that the interitem correlations were sufficiently large for principal component analysis. These statistical measures support the factorability of the data (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2001). Additionally, all the factors derived from the analysis exhibited a Cronbach's alpha coefficient higher than the threshold value of 0.70, demonstrating satisfactory scale reliability (Nunnally, 1978), except "Safety" (SAF) factor (0.60) still in acceptable according to Hair et al., (2010).

As a result of the factor analysis, the scale consisting of 20 items regarding the attitudes towards functional foods was reduced to 5 factors, while the first factor accounted for 14.821% of the total variance, the second factor 18.266% of the total variance, the third factor 12.492% of the total variance, the fourth factor 7.620% of the total variance and the fifth factor explains 16.294% of the total variance. It is seen that these 5 factors explain 69.495% of the total variance (Table 4). The first factor was named "Reward (REW)" because it included statements about the benefits of using functional foods. The second factor was named "Confidence (CON)", as it contains statements of consumers' confidence towards functional foods. In other words, this factor relates to individuals' trust in the information they receive and the strength of their belief in the scientific foundation behind the promised health effects. The third factor was named "Purchase and Consumption Intention (PCI)" because it contains statements about buying and consumption intention towards functional foods. The fourth factor is labeled as "Safety (SAF)," indicating that this dimension reflects respondents' concerns potential negative impacts of functional foods. The fifth and last factor is named "Necessity (NEC)" because it included suspicious statements about the necessity of functional foods (Table 3).

Table 3. Description of Consumers' Attitudes Towards Functional Food Related Scale

Scale Abbreviation, Names and Items	Mean	S.D.	Factor Loading	Variance explained %	Cronbach's α
REWARD (REW)					
REW1. I can prevent disease by eating functional foods regularly	4.03	0.959	0.782	14.821	0.88
REW2. I can protect my health by consuming functional foods	4.32	0.819	0.741		
REW3. I get pleasure from eating functional foods	4.13	0.890	0.718		
REW4. Functional foods make me feel more energetic	4.05	0.908	0.666		
CONFIDENCE (CON)					
CON1. Functional foods are science-based top products	3.73	1.033	0.779	18.266	0.88
CON2. The safety of functional foods has been very thoroughly studied	3.71	1.025	0.767		
CON3. I trust the information given about health effects of functional foods	3.76	0.966	0.759		
CON4. Using functional foods is completely safe	3.69	1.049	0.738		
CON5. I actively seek out information about functional foods	3.07	1.350	0.547		
PURCHASE and CONSUMPTION INTENTION (PCI)					
PCI1. If functional foods are available, I buy it	3.47	1.121	0.760	12.492	0.76
PCI2. It is likely that I will purchase a functional food product soon	3.84	1.009	0.748		
PCI3. I willingly try even unfamiliar products if they are functional	3.62	1.219	0.566		
SAFETY (SAF)					
R1. If used in excess, functional foods can be harmful to health (-)	2.59	1.251	0.842	7.620	0.60
R2. In some cases, functional foods may be harmful for healthy people (-)	2.90	1.405	0.577		
R3. Functional foods are consumed mostly by people who have no need for them (-)	2.75	1.293	0.493		
NECESSITY (NEC)					
NEC1. Functional foods are a total sham (-)	4.00	1.090	0.867	16.294	0.85
NEC2. Functional foods are completely unnecessary (-)	4.12	1.104	0.845		
NEC3. The growing number of functional foods on the market is a bad trend for the future (-)	3.77	1.246	0.790		
NEC4. Exaggerated information is given about health effects (-)	3.28	1.183	0.761		
NEC5. Functional foods carry unforeseen health risks (-)	3.48	1.248	0.655		
KMO=0.890 $\chi^2=4197.516$ df=190 p=0.000					
Total Variance Explained=69.495%					

Note: 1=Strongly disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Slightly agree, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly agree; (-)=Negative statement. This statement were recoded with reversed values before final data analysis.

Table 4 presents the results of an ANOVA analysis and t-test results conducted to examine the potential association between consumers' socio-demographic characteristics and their purchase and consumption intentions toward functional foods. The findings reveal that a significant difference ($p < .05$) was observed between consumers' education, occupation, household size, gender and their purchase and consumption intentions to FFs. Further analysis using the Post Hoc LSD test demonstrated that respondents with bachelor's, master's, and doctorate degrees exhibited a significantly higher intention to purchase and consume functional foods compared to those with a high school education. Additionally, we found that female consumers (3.756) exhibited a more positive response compared to males (3.518). Moreover,

government employees, retirees, and students exhibit higher PCI for FFs compared to the unemployed ones.

Table 4. One Way ANOVA and t-Test Results

Variable	Education	N	Mean	S.D.	F	p	Post Hoc-LSD Test	
	Primary Education (a)	24	3.361	0.715				
	High School (b)	81	3.423	1.012				
	University (c)	195	3.712	0.857	3.234	0.022*	c>b; d>b	
	Master or Doctorate (d)	84	3.769	0.987				
	Total	384	3.642	0.921				
	Occupation							
Purchase and Consumption Intention	Private Sector (a)	125	3.565	1.037				
	Government Employee (b)	174	3.728	0.825				
	Retired (c)	24	3.930	0.735	3.239	0.012*	b>e; c>e; d>e	
	Student (d)	21	3.809	1.035				
	Unemployed (e)	40	3.250	0.866				
	Total	384	3.642	0.921				
Household Size								
	1 (a)	41	3.878	0.884				
	2 (b)	56	3.785	1.011				
	3 (c)	106	3.487	0.888				
	4 (d)	100	3.730	0.899	2.384	0.049*	a>c, e; b>c	
	5+ (e)	81	3.518	0.912				
	Total	384	3.642	0.921				
Gender		N	Mean	S.D.	F	p	t	p
Female		200	3.756	0.897				
Male		184	3.518	0.934	0.118	0.732	2.552	0.011*

Note: *p<0.05

We conducted multiple linear regression analysis to explore the relationship between consumers' attitudes (Necessity, Confidence, Reward, Safety) and their purchase and consumption intentions (PCI) toward functional foods. The results, presented in Table 4, indicate the statistical significance of the regression model (F=94.910; p=.000), explaining a substantial 49.5% of the total variance (Adjusted R²=0.495). Specifically, the analysis reveals a lack of statistically significant relationship between the "Safety" variable and "Purchase and Consumption Intention" ($\beta=0.054, p>.05$). Conversely, the "Reward" variable shows a statistically significant and positive association with "Purchase and Consumption Intention" ($\beta=0.370, p<.05$), as does the "Confidence" variable ($\beta=0.479, p<.05$). Additionally, the "Necessity" variable demonstrates a statistically significant and negative association with "Purchase and Consumption Intention" ($\beta=-0.081, p<.05$). Additionally, hypotheses results are summarized in Table 6.

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression

Variables	β	S.E.	t	p
(Constant)	0.547	0.222	2.461	0.014
NECESSITY (NEC)	-0.081	0.038	-2.110	0.035*
SAFETY (SAF)	0.054	0.039	1.378	0.169
CONFIDENCE (CON)	0.479	0.053	9.121	0.000*
REWARD (REW)	0.370	0.061	6.050	0.000*
Adjusted R²: 0.495; F: 94.910; p: 0.000				

Note: Dependent Variable: Purchase and Consumption Intention (PCI); *p<0.05

Table 6. Hypotheses Test Results

Hypotheses	Relationship	p	Result
H1 _a	Safety ⇒ Purchase and Consumption Intention	0.169	Not Supported
H1 _b	Reward ⇒ Purchase and Consumption Intention	0.000*	Supported
H1 _c	Necessity ⇒ Purchase and Consumption Intention	0.035*	Supported
H1 _d	Confidence ⇒ Purchase and Consumption Intention	0.000*	Supported
H2 _a	Gender ⇒ Purchase and Consumption Intention	0.011*	Supported
H2 _b	Education ⇒ Purchase and Consumption Intention	0.022*	Supported
H2 _c	Occupation ⇒ Purchase and Consumption Intention	0.012*	Supported
H2 _d	Household Size ⇒ Purchase and Consumption Intention	0.049*	Supported

Note: *p<0.05

Discussion

Functional foods, with health-promoting features, are gaining popularity among consumers who prioritize healthy nutrition. While traditional functional products such as Turkish coffee, pickles, herbal teas, and mineral water are well recognized by consumers, this finding aligns with Çelik et al. (2021). However, less familiarity is observed with items like reduced-fat and sugar-free ice cream, low-sodium salt, and fiber-enriched bars among the surveyed population.

Our study aligns with prior research (Poulsen, 1999; Verbeke, 2005; Urala and Lähteenmäki, 2007; Landström et al., 2007; Ares et al., 2009; Sääksjärvi et al., 2009; Vecchio et al., 2016; Vicentini et al., 2016; Ali and Rahut, 2019; Karelakis et al., 2020), confirming that predominantly female and higher-educated respondents exhibit more positive intentions toward purchasing and consuming functional foods. The positive association between education degree and intentions suggests that higher education correlates with a better understanding of potential health benefits. Additionally, Post Hoc tests revealed that individuals in smaller households exhibit more positive intentions towards functional foods compared to those in larger households, aligning with Markovina et al.'s (2011) findings.

Our findings indicate generally positive attitudes towards the rewards of using functional foods among respondents, aligned with previous research (Aschemann-Witzel and Grunert, 2015; Karelakis et al., 2020). Respondents believe that consuming functional foods contributes to health protection, pleasure, and increased energy, reflecting a perception of these foods as valuable for well-being. Notably, there's a significant agreement among consumers that functional foods are unnecessary and even considered a total sham, signaling skepticism and a lack of trust in the industry. The growing number of functional foods seen as a negative trend for the future raises concerns.

In line with prior studies (Somehagen et al., 2013; Nystrand and Olsen, 2020; Salmani et al., 2020; Moodi et al., 2021) both the "Reward" and "Confidence" variables exhibit a statistically significant impact on PCI to FFs. This indicates that consumers who derive rewards from using functional foods and have confidence in their benefits are more likely to purchase and consume them. Moreover, the "Necessity" variable shows a statistically significant and negative association with "Purchase and Consumption Intention," implying that consumers may be less motivated to engage with functional foods when they perceive them as less necessary. This finding aligns with previous research showing that consumer skepticism negatively impacts the perceived value and purchase intentions of health-related products. Ciccìu and Carmona (2024) found that skepticism reduces the perceived value of organic foods, lowering purchase intentions.

Conclusions and Implications

This study explores functional food consumption across various Turkish cities, highlighting traditional products such as Turkish coffee, tarhana chips and soup, and fermented black carrot juice (Şalgam). While functional foods provide health benefits, excessive consumption may lead to risks, such as caffeine-related effects from high Turkish coffee intake. Şalgam, known for its probiotic and antioxidant properties, has strong export potential—not only in Mediterranean markets but also in regions like North America and Scandinavia, where there is growing interest in traditional and gut-friendly fermented beverages.

Key findings highlight the importance of public awareness campaigns and transparent marketing to address consumer skepticism. "Reward" and "Confidence" positively impact Purchase and Consumption Intention (PCI), emphasizing the need for health-focused messaging. Conversely, the negative association between "Necessity" and PCI suggests that businesses should highlight essential product benefits to enhance perceived necessity.

Demographic factors such as education, occupation, household size, and gender influence purchasing intentions. Consumers from smaller households show greater willingness to buy FFs, suggesting a market for individually packaged options. Women respond more positively to FFs, presenting an opportunity for targeted health- and taste-focused promotions. These insights help businesses refine marketing strategies to increase consumer acceptance and adoption of functional foods.

Research Limitations and Hints for Future Research

This research is limited by the data collection period coinciding with the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite the online survey's convenience, obtaining feedback was challenging due to restrictions and the pandemic's negative psychological impact on individuals, likely contributing to the low response rate. For researchers who want to study in this area, it can be suggested that should keep the sample size at higher levels, and increase the number of cities surveyed during the data collection phase. Moreover, the sample size lacked homogeneity, particularly in terms of education and income levels. Our online surveys were less effective in reaching respondents with lower education and income, resulting in fewer responses from these groups. Future research should aim for a more balanced and diverse representation across various demographic groups. Additionally, for future studies, it is advisable to delve deeper into consumer behavior towards functional foods using advanced methods like Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE). These methods offer a nuanced analysis of preferences and choices, providing valuable insights into the complex dynamics of consumer decision-making in the functional foods domain.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Ali, A., & Rahut, D. B. (2019). Healthy foods as proxy for functional foods: Consumers' awareness, perception, and demand for natural functional foods in Pakistan. *International Journal of Food Science*, 2019, Article 6390650. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/6390650>
- Altındış, M., İnci, M. B., Elmas, B., Şahin, E. Ö., Kahraman, E. P., Karagöz, R., Küçükkara, G., & Altındış, S. (2018). Aile hekimleri, pediatristler ve eczacıların probiyotik kullanımları hakkında bilgi, tutum ve davranışları. *Journal of Biotechnology and Strategic Health Research*, 2(2), 108–116.
- Annunziata, A., & Vecchio, R. (2013). Consumer perception of functional foods: A conjoint analysis with probiotics. *Food Quality and Preference*, 28(1), 348–355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2012.10.009>
- Anttolainen, M., Luoto, R., Uutela, A., Boice, J. D., Blot, W. J., McLaughlin, J. K., & Puska, P. (2001). Characteristics of users and nonusers of plant stanol ester margarine in Finland: An approach to study functional foods. *Journal of the American Dietetic Association*, 101(11), 1365–1368. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-8223\(01\)00325-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-8223(01)00325-7)
- Arai, S. (2002). Global view on functional foods: Asian perspectives. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 88(S2), S139–S143. <https://doi.org/10.1079/BJN2002683>
- Ares, G., & Gámbaro, A. (2007). Influence of gender, age and motives underlying food choice on perceived healthiness and willingness to try functional foods. *Appetite*, 49(1), 148–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2007.01.006>
- Ares, G., Giménez, A., & Gámbaro, A. (2009). Consumer perceived healthiness and willingness to try functional milk desserts: Influence of ingredient, ingredient name and health claim. *Food Quality and Preference*, 20(1), 50–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2008.07.002>
- Aschemann-Witzel, J., & Grunert, K. G. (2015). Influence of 'soft' versus 'scientific' health information framing and contradictory information on consumers' health inferences and attitudes towards a food supplement. *Food Quality and Preference*, 42, 90–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2015.01.009>
- Bagchi, D. (Ed.). (2014). *Nutraceutical and functional food regulations in the United States and around the world* (2nd ed.). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2011-0-07516-7>
- Baglione, S. L., Tucci, L. A., & Stanton, J. L. (2012). Self-reported nutritional knowledge and the acceptance of health-related food benefit claims. *British Food Journal*, 114(4), 453–468. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00070701211219506>
- Beardsworth, A., Haslam, C., Keil, T., Goode, J., & Sherratt, E. (1999). Contemporary nutritional attitudes and practices: A factor analysis approach. *Appetite*, 32(2), 127–143. <https://doi.org/10.1006/appe.1998.0188>
- Bekoglu, F. B., Ergen, A., & İnci, B. (2016). The impact of attitude, consumer innovativeness and interpersonal influence on functional food consumption. *Journal of International Business Research*, 9(2), 79–87.
- Benkouider, C. (2005). The world's emerging markets. *Functional Foods and Nutraceuticals*, 14–17.
- Bigliardi, B., & Galati, F. (2013). Innovation trends in the food industry: The case of functional foods. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 31(2), 118–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2013.03.006>
- Boluda, K., & Capilla, V. (2017). Consumer attitudes in the election of functional foods. *Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC*, 21(1), 65–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjme.2016.12.001>

- Carrillo, E., Prado-Gascó, V., Fiszman, S., & Varela, P. (2013). Why buying functional foods? Understanding spending behavior through structural equation modelling. *Food Research International*, 50(1), 361–368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2012.11.031>
- Cavaliere, A., Ricci, E. C., & Banterle, A. (2015). Nutrition and health claims: Who is interested? An empirical analysis of consumer preferences in Italy. *Food Quality and Preference*, 41, 44–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2014.11.002>
- Çelik, A. D. (2023). Consumers' perceptions about probiotic food products and their effects on purchase intention: A case study of Eastern Mediterranean Region of Turkey. *New Medit*, 23(4), 140–154. <https://doi.org/10.30682/nm2304h>
- Çelik, H., & Gül, A. (2023). Consumer perceptions and purchase intentions towards organic foods: Evidence from Eastern Mediterranean Region of Türkiye. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 41(11), 275–291. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajaees/2023/v41i112285>
- Çelik, H., Çelik, A. D., Hayran, S., & Gül, A. (2021). Knowledge level and consumption tendency of university students about functional foods: A case study of Çukurova University. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture - Food Science and Technology*, 9(7), 1242–1249. <https://doi.org/10.24925/turjaf.v9i7.1242-1249.4260>
- Chen, M. (2011). The joint moderating effect of health consciousness and healthy lifestyle on consumers' willingness to use functional foods in Taiwan. *Appetite*, 57(1), 253–262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2011.05.305>
- Churchill, G. A. (1995). *Marketing research: Methodological foundations* (6th ed.). The Dryden Press, Harcourt Brace College Publishers.
- Cicciù, B., & Carmona, L. J. D. M. (2024). The impact of consumer skepticism on the perceived value of organic food and purchase intention. *Revista de Administração da UFES*, 17, e8. <https://doi.org/10.5902/1983465985505>
- Contini, C., Grunert, K., Christensen, R. N., Boncinelli, F., Scozzafava, G., & Casini, L. (2023). Does attitude moderate the effect of labelling information when choosing functional foods? *Food Quality and Preference*, 106, 104795. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2023.104795>
- Di Pasquale, J., Adinolfi, F., & Capitanio, F. (2011). Analysis of consumer attitudes and consumers willingness to pay for functional foods. *International Journal on Food System Dynamics*, 2(2), 181–193. <https://doi.org/10.18461/ijfsd.v2i2.226>
- Eser, A. G. (2017). Probiyotikler konusunda tüketicilerin ilgi ve kanaatleri: Çanakkale-Biga örneği. *Van Veterinary Journal*, 28(1), 25–30.
- Fantechi, T., Contini, C., & Casini, L. (2023). Pasta goes green: Consumer preferences for spirulina-enriched pasta in Italy. *Algal Research*, 75, 103275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2023.103275>
- Gewers, F. L., Ferreira, G. R., Arruda, H. F. D., Silva, F. N., Comin, C. H., Amancio, D. R., & Costa, L. D. F. (2021). Principal component analysis: A natural approach to data exploration. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 54(4), 1–34. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3447555>
- Gezginç, Y., & Gök, S. (2016). Adana ili örneği ile tüketicilerin fonksiyonel gıdalara yönelik farkındalığı. *Atatürk Üniversitesi Ziraat Fakültesi Dergisi*, 47(2), 101–106.
- Gök, İ. (2023). Functional potential of several Turkish fermented traditional foods: Biotic properties, bioactive compounds, and health benefits. *Food Reviews International*, 39(5), 2568–2593. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87559129.2021.1962340>

- Gök, İ., & Ulu, E. K. (2018). Functional foods in Turkey: Marketing, consumer awareness and regulatory aspects. *Nutrition & Food Science*, 48(6), 915–930. <https://doi.org/10.1108/NFS-01-2018-0010>
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2010). *Multivariate data analysis: A global perspective* (6th ed.). Pearson.
- Henry, C. (2010). Editorial: Functional foods. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 64(7), 657–659.
- Institute of Food Technologists. (2020). Global migration: Emerging opportunities in food and drink. *Food Technology Magazine*. Retrieved from <https://www.ift.org/news-and-publications/food-technology-magazine/issues/2019/october/features/global-migration-emerging-opportunities-in-food-and-drink>
- Iwatani, S., & Yamamoto, N. (2019). Functional food products in Japan: A review. *Food Science and Human Wellness*, 8(2), 96–101.
- Jeżewska-Zychowicz, M. (2009). Impact of beliefs and attitudes on young consumers' willingness to use functional food. *Polish Journal of Food and Nutrition Sciences*, 59(2), 183–187.
- Karelakis, C., Zevgitis, P., Galanopoulos, K., & Mattas, K. (2020). Consumer trends and attitudes to functional foods. *Journal of International Food & Agribusiness Marketing*, 32(3), 266–294.
- Kljusurić, J. G., Čačić, J., Misir, A., & Čačić, D. (2015). Geographical region as a factor influencing consumers' perception of functional food: The case of Croatia. *British Food Journal*, 117(3), 1017–1031.
- Kojima, K. (1996). The eastern consumer viewpoint: The experience in Japan. *Nutrition Reviews*, 54(11), S186–S188.
- Kraus, A., Annunziata, A., & Vecchio, R. (2017). Sociodemographic factors differentiating the consumer and the motivations for functional food consumption. *Journal of the American College of Nutrition*, 36(2), 116–126.
- Kurkcu, B., Üstünsoy, E., & Dedeoğlu, B. B. (2023). Do health anxiety and social value shape the intention to consume functional food: The role of health knowledge levels—Evidence from Istanbul. *British Food Journal*, 125(10), 3553–3572. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-12-2022-1050>
- Labrecque, J., Doyon, M., Bellavance, F., & Kolodinsky, J. (2006). Acceptance of functional foods: A comparison of French, American, and French Canadian consumers. *Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 54(4), 647–661.
- Landström, E. (2008). *To choose or not to choose functional foods, that is the question: Swedish consumers' and health-care professionals' attitudes to use of functional foods* (Doctoral dissertation, Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis).
- Landström, E., Hursti, U. K. K., Becker, W., & Magnusson, M. (2007). Use of functional foods among Swedish consumers is related to health-consciousness and perceived effect. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 98(5), 1058–1069.
- Markosyan, A., McCluskey, J. J., & Wahl, T. I. (2009). Consumer response to information about a functional food product: Apples enriched with antioxidants. *Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economics/Revue canadienne d'agroeconomie*, 57(3), 325–341. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-7976.2009.01153.x>
- Markovina, J., Čačić, J., Kljusurić, J. G., & Kovačić, D. (2011). Young consumers' perception of functional foods in Croatia. *British Food Journal*, 113(1), 7–16. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00070701111097352>
- Martirosyan, D. M., & Singh, J. (2015). A new definition of functional food by FFC: What makes a definition unique? *Functional Foods in Health and Disease*, 5(6), 209–223. <https://doi.org/10.31989/ffhd.v5i6.183>

- Migliore, G., Rizzo, G., Bonanno, A., Dudinskaya, E. C., Tóth, J., & Schifani, G. (2022). Functional food characteristics in organic food products—the perspectives of Italian consumers on organic eggs enriched with omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids. *Organic Agriculture*, 12, 149–161. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-021-00366-0>
- Moodi, M., Salmani, F., Norozi, E., & Zeinali, T. (2021). Predictors of functional dairy product consumption among Iranian consumers. *International Dairy Journal*, 121, 105061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idairyj.2021.105061>
- Nakip, M. (2006). *Pazarlama arařtırmaları: Teknikler ve SPSS destekli uygulamalar* [Marketing research: Techniques and SPSS-supported applications]. Seçkin Yayıncılık.
- Nations Online Project. (n.d.). *Map of Türkiye*. Retrieved January 28, 2024, from <https://www.nationsonline.org/oneworld/map/turkey-map.htm>
- Nazzaro, C., Stanco, M., Uliano, A., & Marotta, G. (2024). Consumers' acceptance and willingness to pay for enriched foods: Evidence from a choice experiment in Italy. *Future Foods*, 100405. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fufo.2024.100405>
- Niva, M., & Mäkelä, J. (2007). Finns and functional foods: Socio-demographics, health efforts, notions of technology and the acceptability of health-promoting foods. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 31(1), 34–45. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1470-6431.2006.00482.x>
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978). *Psychometric theory* (2nd ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Nystrand, B. T., & Olsen, S. O. (2020). Consumers' attitudes and intentions toward consuming functional foods in Norway. *Food Quality and Preference*, 80, 103827. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2019.103827>
- Ozen, A. E., del Mar Bibiloni, M., Pons, A., & Tur, J. A. (2013). Sociodemographic and lifestyle determinants of functional food consumption in an adult population of the Balearic Islands. *Annals of Nutrition and Metabolism*, 63(3), 200–207. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000354907>
- Poulsen, J. B. (1999). *Danish consumers' attitudes towards functional foods* (MAPP Working Paper No. 62). Aarhus: MAPP—Centre for Market Surveillance, Research and Strategy for the Food Sector.
- Puhakka, R., Valve, R., & Sinkkonen, A. (2017). Older consumers' perceptions of functional foods and non-edible health-enhancing innovations. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 42(1), 111–119. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12399>
- Qin, W., & Brown, J. L. (2008). Factors explaining male/female differences in attitudes and purchase intention toward genetically engineered salmon. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 7(2), 127–145. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cb.241>
- Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Climate Change. (2020a). *Adana ili hakkında* [About Adana province]. Retrieved December 31, 2020, from <https://adana.csb.gov.tr/ilimizitaniyalim-i-1222>
- Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Climate Change. (2020b). *Kahramanmaraş ili hakkında* [About Kahramanmaraş province]. Retrieved December 31, 2020, from <https://kahramanmaras.csb.gov.tr/ilimiz-hakkinda-i-824>
- Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Environment, Urbanisation and Climate Change. (2020c). *Osmaniye ili hakkında* [About Osmaniye province]. Retrieved December 31, 2020, from <https://osmaniye.csb.gov.tr/ilimiz-hakkinda-i-100530>
- Republic of Türkiye Hatay Governorship. (n.d.). Nüfus ve Dağılımı. Retrieved December 1, 2023, from <http://www.hatay.gov.tr/nufus-ve-dagilimi>

- Sääksjärvi, M., Holmlund, M., & Tanskanen, N. (2009). Consumer knowledge of functional foods. *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 19(2), 135–156. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593960903206740>
- Salmani, F., Norozi, E., Moodi, M., & Zeinali, T. (2020). Assessment of attitudes toward functional foods based on theory of planned behavior: Validation of a questionnaire. *Nutrition Journal*, 19(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12937-020-00545-0>
- Schnettler, B., Miranda, H., Lobos, G., Sepúlveda, J., Orellana, L., Mora, M., & Grunert, K. (2015). Willingness to purchase functional foods according to their benefits. *British Food Journal*, 117(5), 1453–1473. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BJFJ-08-2014-0292>
- Seçer, A., Kantar Davran, M., Tok, N., Emeksiz, F., Akbay, C., & Tapkı, N. (2014). Akademisyenlerin fonksiyonel gıdalara yönelik algılarının ve tutumlarının belirlenmesi: Doğu Akdeniz Bölgesi üniversiteleri örneği. In *XI. Ulusal Tarım Ekonomisi Kongresi* (pp. 1277–1285). Samsun.
- Sevilmiş, G. (2008). *A research on consumer decision about some kinds of functional foods and determining factors which affect it* (Master's thesis). Ege University, Institute of Natural and Applied Sciences, Department of Agricultural Economics, İzmir.
- Sevilmiş, G., Olgun, A., & Artukoğlu, M. (2017). A research on the factors affecting consumer decisions in functional foods: The example of İzmir province. *Journal of Ege University Faculty of Agriculture*, 54(3), 351–360.
- Somehagen, J., Holmes, C., & Saleh, R. (2013). *Functional food: A study of consumer attitude towards functional foods in Sweden* (Bachelor's thesis). Linnaeus University, School of Business and Economics, Sweden.
- Stähle, L., & Wold, S. (1989). Analysis of variance (ANOVA). *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems*, 6(4), 259–272. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-7439\(89\)80095-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-7439(89)80095-4)
- Sundaram, K. R., Dwivedi, S. N., & Sreenivas, V. (2014). *Medical statistics: Principles and methods* (2nd ed.). New Delhi: Wolters Kluwer, India.
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2001). *Using multivariate statistics* (4th ed.). Boston, MA: Allyn and Bacon.
- Teratanavat, R., & Hooker, N. H. (2006). Consumer valuations and preference heterogeneity for a novel functional food. *Journal of Food Science*, 71(7), S533–S541. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-3841.2006.00160.x>
- U.S. Department of Agriculture, Foreign Agricultural Service. (2019). Turkey's advanced food sector provides opportunities in spite of economic downturn. Retrieved from [https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Turkey%2027s%20Advanced%20Food%20Sector%20Provides%20Opportunities%20in%20Spite%20of%20Economic%20Downturn Ankara Turkey 11-15-2019](https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Turkey%2027s%20Advanced%20Food%20Sector%20Provides%20Opportunities%20in%20Spite%20of%20Economic%20Downturn%20Ankara%20Turkey%2011-15-2019)
- Urala, N., & Lähteenmäki, L. (2004). Attitudes behind consumers' willingness to use functional foods. *Food Quality and Preference*, 15(7–8), 793–803. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2004.02.008>
- Urala, N., & Lähteenmäki, L. (2007). Consumers' changing attitudes towards functional foods. *Food Quality and Preference*, 18(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2005.06.007>
- Urala, N., Schutz, H., & Spinks, J. (2011). Consumer perceptions of "functional food" in the United States. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 17(5), 407–419. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10454446.2011.618964>
- Vecchio, R., Van Loo, E. J., & Annunziata, A. (2016). Consumers' willingness to pay for conventional, organic and functional yogurt: Evidence from experimental auctions. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 40(3), 368–378. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12256>

- Verbeke, W. (2005). Consumer acceptance of functional foods: Socio-demographic, cognitive and attitudinal determinants. *Food Quality and Preference*, 16(1), 45–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2004.01.001>
- Vicentini, A., Liberatore, L., & Mastrocola, D. (2016). Functional foods: Trends and development of the global market. *Italian Journal of Food Science*, 28(2), 228–241. <https://doi.org/10.14674/1120-1770/ijfs.v28i2.607>
- Welsch, S. (1996). Nutrient standards, dietary guidelines and food guides. In E. E. Ziegler & L. J. Filer (Eds.), *Present knowledge in nutrition* (pp. 745–754). ILSI Press.
- Whitley, E., & Ball, J. (2002). Statistics review 5: Comparison of means. *Critical Care*, 6(5), 424–428. <https://doi.org/10.1186/cc1524>
- Yeon Kim, H., & Chung, J. (2011). Consumer purchase intention for organic personal care products. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 28(1), 40–47. <https://doi.org/10.1108/07363761111101930>
- Yilmaz-Ersan, L., Ozcan, T., & Akpınar-Bayızit, A. (2020). Assessment of socio-demographic factors, health status and the knowledge on probiotic dairy products. *Food Science and Human Wellness*, 9(3), 272–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fshw.2020.04.002>

Appendix

Table 2. Functional Food Recognition and Consumption Frequency of Consumers

Functional Foods	1		2		3		4		5		Total	Mean	S.D.	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%				
Probiotic milk	39	10.2	134	34.9	78	20.3	71	18.5	62	16.1	384	100	2.96	1.260
Probiotic yogurt	27	7	119	31	83	21.6	85	22.1	70	18.2	384	100	3.14	1.236
Kefir	13	3.4	68	17.7	110	28.6	94	24.5	99	25.8	384	100	3.52	1.152
Cheese with low fat	15	3.9	71	18.5	135	35.2	105	27.3	58	15.1	384	100	3.31	1.060
Breakfast cereals	23	6.0	73	19.0	146	38.0	80	20.8	62	16.1	384	100	3.22	1.113
Whole grain bread	9	2.3	34	8.9	113	29.4	103	26.8	125	32.6	384	100	3.78	1.068
Cereal diet biscuits	17	4.4	68	17.7	134	34.9	93	24.2	72	18.8	384	100	3.35	1.107
Salt with reduced sodium	65	16.9	106	27.6	116	30.2	68	17.7	29	7.6	384	100	2.71	1.164
Lactose free milk	32	8.3	107	27.9	124	32.3	60	15.6	61	15.9	384	100	3.03	1.186
Ice cream with reduced fat and sugar	66	17.2	144	37.5	114	29.7	44	11.5	16	4.2	384	100	2.48	1.037
Gluten free foods	28	7.3	133	34.6	126	32.8	70	18.2	27	7.0	384	100	2.83	1.037
Herbal teas	-	-	39	10.2	105	27.3	111	28.9	129	33.6	384	100	3.85	1.011
Mineral water	-	-	24	6.3	84	21.9	99	25.8	177	46.0	384	100	4.11	0.965
Chocolate-Cocoa	-	-	36	9.4	106	27.6	108	28.1	134	34.9	384	100	3.88	1.001
Fiber added bars	42	10.9	88	22.9	122	31.8	69	18.0	63	16.4	384	100	3.06	1.226
Pickles	-	-	24	6.2	72	18.8	80	20.8	208	54.2	384	100	4.22	0.979
Tarhana chips and soup	-	-	29	7.5	102	26.6	88	22.9	165	43.0	384	100	4.03	1.091
Turkish coffee	-	-	21	5.5	73	19.0	76	19.8	214	55.7	384	100	4.26	0.950
Artichoke	17	4.4	83	21.6	121	31.5	67	17.4	96	25.0	384	100	3.37	1.198
Broccoli	6	1.6	33	8.6	114	29.7	89	23.2	142	37.0	384	100	3.85	1.064
Radish	-	-	30	7.8	94	24.5	100	26.0	160	41.7	384	100	4.01	0.995
Liver	-	-	68	17.7	112	29.2	113	29.4	91	23.7	384	100	3.58	1.051
Fish	-	-	23	6.0	76	19.8	113	29.4	172	44.8	384	100	4.13	0.940
Fermented black carrot juice	-	-	31	8.0	94	24.5	112	29.2	147	38.3	384	100	3.97	0.989

Note: 1=I do not recognize this product, 2=I recognize this product, but I have not tasted it, 3=I have tasted this product, but I do not use it, 4=I use this product occasionally, 5=I use this product frequently.

